

Bengal Journal of Social Science and Development

Volume No. 3, Issue No. 4 (Dec, 2024) | ISSN: 2583-3413

An Online Quarterly Published Peer Reviewed Journal for Social Science Disciplines
by N.S.D. Educational Welfare Trust

E-Journal URL: www.bjssd-journal.com

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Barriers to Developing Listening and Speaking Skills at the Secondary Level: A Study in the Context of Dhaka City, Bangladesh

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the barriers to listening and speaking skills in secondary education in Dhaka City. Listening and speaking skills are essential components of effective communication and play a vital role in academic and professional success. However, students often encounter various obstacles that impede the development and mastery of these skills. Understanding these barriers is crucial for educators, policymakers, and researchers to design strategies to enhance listening and speaking proficiency among secondary-level students. A mixed-method approach was employed to achieve the research objectives. Firstly, an extensive literature review was conducted to identify the existing theoretical frameworks, concepts, and empirical studies related to listening and speaking skill barriers. This review formed the foundation for constructing a research questionnaire and interview protocol. The study sample consisted of secondary school students from different educational institutions in Dhaka City. The questionnaire collected quantitative data on students' perceptions of listening and speaking skill barriers, encompassing factors such as classroom environment, instructional practices, student motivation, and linguistic challenges. Additionally, interviews were conducted with teachers to gather qualitative insights into their perspectives on the barriers and potential solutions. The findings revealed several significant barriers to listening and speaking skills in secondary education, including inadequate

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classroom infrastructure, limited opportunities for interactive communication, ineffective teaching methods, lack of motivation, and language proficiency issues. Furthermore, the research identified potential strategies to address these barriers, such as creating supportive classroom environments, promoting active participation, integrating speaking and listening activities, and fostering student motivation. Teachers can benefit from the findings by adapting instructional strategies to create interactive and communicative learning environments, and addressing student-specific challenges, and promoting oral proficiency. By identifying these barriers and suggesting potential solutions, it offers valuable guidance for educators, policymakers, and researchers to enhance listening and speaking skill instruction, fostering effective communication and academic achievement among secondary school students.

Keywords: *Barrier, curriculum, Dhaka city, listening, secondary level, speaking*

1. Introduction

English serves as a widely used language for communication across different linguistic communities, commonly referred to as a lingua franca. In Bangladesh, it is mandated that English will be taught as a mandatory subject at the secondary level. In order to effectively instruct a language, it is imperative to incorporate four essential skills. The four essential language skills encompassed in language learning are listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The majority of students primarily receive instruction in reading and writing skills, with limited opportunities to develop their listening and speaking abilities. The objective of this study is to identify the primary obstacles encountered in the development of listening and speaking abilities. In Bangladesh, the educational curriculum places a significant emphasis on the development of reading and writing abilities. Consequently, a substantial number of students rely heavily on their proficiency in reading comprehension and writing composition (Matin, 2012, p. 239). Additionally, teachers tend to avoid incorporating listening and speaking activities into their lessons due to factors such as large class sizes or a lack of sufficient materials. Hence, it can be observed that both listening and speaking abilities have assumed a secondary role within the context of Bangladesh. Currently, there is a significant focus within our education system on enhancing students' proficiency in English communication.

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Education planners at the secondary level tend to allocate less importance to the development of speaking and listening skills, despite the fact that these two modalities are widely recognized as fundamental forms of communication. Simultaneously, educational institutions and curricula fail to offer students ample opportunities for enhancing these aforementioned skills. The educational materials provided by the educational board consist of various chapters and exercises designed to enhance learners' skills. However, it has been observed that these resources may not fully meet the needs of the learners. Both students and teachers commonly prioritize the completion of the syllabus over the enhancement of their skills. Moreover, due to the prevailing circumstances in which students find themselves, they are deprived of the chance to engage in English communication. Effective communication requires accurate listening. Failure to listen attentively can hinder one's ability to effectively communicate. Listening is widely recognized as a crucial skill in the realm of language acquisition and pedagogy. In order to optimize one's proficiency in listening and speaking, it is imperative to dedicate considerable effort towards enhancing one's vocabulary, mastering correct pronunciation, and acquiring a solid grasp of linguistic structures.

2. Literature Review

Proficiency is never achieved by honing only two abilities, namely reading and writing. Any student who wants to be an expert in the English language, particularly in communication, must be equally adept in all four areas. While Hymes (as reported in Abedin, Majlish, & Akter, 2009) said that the goal of language training is "communicative competence". This idea makes it clear that four skills are equally crucial for teaching and learning languages. The pupils need to be in a setting where both the instructor and learner speak the same language. English is the means of communication in the classroom and is also the target language. But this circumstance does not exist in Bangladesh.

According to Rixon (quoted in Abedin, Majlish, and Akter, 2009), acquiring English as a second language should emphasize attentiveness. He asserts that various skills are interdependent when listening. There is a distinction between hearing and attention in ordinary life. Hearing is merely the recognition of stimuli, as in "I'm sorry, I didn't hear exactly what you said." Listening

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entails paying some degree of conscious attention to the message that is being communicated, as when one states, “Are you listening to me?” This distinction is beneficial when considering the various abilities; a pupil uses to comprehend spoken English. He also demonstrates how native speakers’ pronunciation of English can pose difficulties for students in terms of recognition and, consequently, comprehension. There are four primary causes of listening difficulties: the weak relationship between English sounds and their spelling in the written language, changes in sounds when they occur in rapid and connected speech, the rhythm pattern of English speech, and different ways of pronouncing the same sound.

According to Harmer, “One skill cannot be performed without the other.” People cannot communicate in a conversation if they do not listen well, and they rarely write without reading” (52). Speaking is commonly regarded as one of the most essential productive abilities. As suggested by McDonough and Shaw (1993, p.152), “as a skill that enables us to produce utterances, when truly communicatively, speaking is desire and purpose-driven,” i.e., we want to communicate something to achieve a specific goal.

The ability to communicate a language fluently indicates proficiency in that language. A person can write without proper knowledge of grammar and sentence structure; they can read without proper pronunciation; and they can listen without proper listening skills; however, speaking ability is dependent on the total knowledge of a language (vocabulary, grammar, sentence structure, listening, and so on.). One not only communicates but also listens during interactions. If one uses improper English, one fails to communicate effectively and receives immediate feedback regarding this failure. It is an essential component of daily interaction. The first impression of a person’s language ability is based on his or her ability to communicate fluently and thoroughly.

According to Brown and Yule (as cited in Kabir, 2014), language serves two functions: information transfer (transactional function) and sustaining social relationships (interactional function). Interactional spoken language is characterized by topic changes and brief turns rather than precision and clarity. In contrast to interactional language, which is “listener-oriented,” transactional language is “message-oriented” (11-16). Additionally, oral English is essential for

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developing reading and writing abilities. It means when one reads and writes, one relies on one's oral language knowledge.

Penny (1984, p. 30) acknowledged the significance of listening in the English language classroom because it is vital to the development of learners' perception and comprehension skills and serves as a foundation for classroom study and discussion. English education in Bangladesh has experienced numerous ups and downs. During the British era, the purpose of mastering English was to create a subordinate class. They were only instructed in English reading and writing. Gradually, however, the circumstance has shifted, and thus the emphasis on teaching and acquiring English has also shifted. In 1998-1999, the Communicative Approach or CLT was implemented in Bangladesh in order to enable students to speak English in real-world situations.

However, this innovation was not well received by our English instructors. Selim and Tasneem (as cited in Kabir, 2014) criticize these ELT instructors by stating, "When CLT arrived in Bangladesh, traditional English teachers opposed it vehemently because they were not prepared for something new"(7).The teachers rarely felt the need to teach spoken and listening skills, as they were quite successful without focusing on these two crucial aspects of language acquisition.

In Bangladesh, English for Today or EFT remains the primary source for teaching English. As the book's inspiration, EFT is an excellent resource for teaching and learning spoken English, thereby fostering students' communicative competence. According to Kabir (2014), Billah has tallied and categorized the EFT books' English teachings. He discovered that the number of listening comprehension lessons in the EFT book for sixth grade is eight out of 106, ten out of eighty, eleven out of seventy-five, and twenty-two out of one hundred and ninety. The results indicate that the number of listening lessons is insufficient compared to the total number of lessons. However, the scenario is distinct when spoken. For instance, there are 80 speaking-focused courses in sixth grade, 74 in seventh grade, 69 in eighth grade EFT, and 63 in ninth grade. This indicates that these EFT books are the primary focus of the speaking skill.

3. Theoretical framework

American sociolinguist Dell Hymes coined the term "communicative competence" to contradict Noam Chomsky's linguistic competence and performance paradigm. Communicative competence

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in CLT is a linguistic term that alludes to a learner's capacity to form and use correct utterances in the target language.

The CLT methodology originated with linguists such as Dell Hymes and Michael Halliday, who viewed language primarily as a means of communication. Numerous researchers have contributed to the theory and practice of CLT's development. Communicative language instruction (CLT) encompasses four fundamental abilities. This includes hearing, speaking, reading, and writing. All of these skills are essential for the development of the English language. However, the point is that not all talents are taught equally in secondary school. The testing system, curriculum, and instructional methodology all place exclusive emphasis on reading and writing. The two most important abilities, hearing and communicating, are not assessed.

The listening and speaking skills adhere to a number of theories and methods, such as Krashen, Behaviorist theory, Mentalist theory, Innatist theory, Grammar Translation methods, Audio Lingual method, and so on. By introducing the concept of comprehensible input, Krashen integrates listening-based methods. According to Krashen and Terrell (1983), the acquisition is only possible when individuals can comprehend messages in the target language.

4. Methodology

To conduct the research, random data sources must be identified and collected, then categorized, analyzed, interpreted, and presented in a systematic manner. This study relies heavily on primary data. Six institutions within the city of Dhaka have provided the primary data.

4.1. Section of the Study Area

In order to conduct the research, six institutions from the Dhaka metropolitan area have been chosen. Two of these six are government institutions, while the remaining four are private. These institutions are Government Laboratory High School Dhaka, Government High School Tejgaon, Kurmitola High School, Adamjee Cantonment Public School, Barna Mala Adarsha High School, and BAF Shaheen School.

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4.2. Population (Respondents) of the Study

The respondents of this study include secondary school students and instructors in the Dhaka metropolitan region. Random sampling is used to choose a sample from a population.

4.3. Determination of the sampling size

For the purposes of this study, 88 samples are randomly selected from instructors and students. The sample consists of both teachers and students. Six schools are used to choose 70 students and 18 teachers.

4.4. Data Collection

Two sets of questionnaires, one for instructors and the other for students, are used to capture information from multiple sources. The questionnaire was administered to secondary school instructors and pupils in the Dhaka metropolitan area in order to collect data for this study. The query was of the closed-ended variety, in which students had the option to select an answer. And interviews are conducted with only English instructors.

4.5. Sources of Data

For this research, primary and secondary data sources are used to better comprehend the topic at hand and to meet the study's goals.

4.6. Primary Data Collection

Primary data are the major source for this research. Here, primary data were gathered via a questionnaire. A total of six schools in the Dhaka metropolitan region have provided data. Two of these six institutions are government schools, while the other four are not. This poll was carried out in November 2022.

4.7. Secondary Data Collection

For the fundamental and pertinent information of the research, secondary data were gathered with the aid of several books, reports, articles, papers, journals, and other published publications linked to speaking and listening abilities.

4.8. Questionnaire Preparation

Primary data from sources is collected using a standardized questionnaire. Teachers and students

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get two questionnaires.

4.9. Data Processing

After the necessary survey, data has been gathered, and the following two steps are taken to analyze the study’s findings: assembling and editing data.

4.10. Data Compilation

The information has been organized, categorized, and then methodically compiled in accordance with the goals.

4.11. Data Editing

The collected primary data have been edited to remove any errors and omissions. The collected data have also been meticulously implied and categorized for a more effective analysis.

4.12. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Various planning and statistical tools and techniques have been utilized to explain, interpret, and analyze the collated data. SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science), Microsoft Word, and Excel are utilized to process the data. According to the study’s objective and hypothesis, the collected data have been interpreted and analyzed. The analysis is displayed in a variety of column charts.

4.12.1. Survey Questions (for Instructors)

1. The importance of current text book

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According to Figure 1, 33.3% of respondents believe that the present English textbook is useful for students' listening and speaking abilities, 11.1% believe that the textbook is not helpful, and 55.6% think that the textbook is only moderately helpful.

2. The chances of open conversation for the students

Figure 2 demonstrates that 50% of teachers provide their students with the opportunity for free discussion. On the other side, 16.7% of instructors seldom allow their students the opportunity for free discussion, while 11.1% of teachers do not give chances for open conversation to their students, Finally, 22.2% of teachers think that they must contribute in some way. This is fairly satisfactory, but it needs more attention since students are constantly given the possibility to engage in open discussion, which will boost their speaking ability and confidence.

3. Ability of understanding teacher’s speech while speaking in English

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According to the data presented in the Figure 3, it is evident that a majority of learners, specifically 57.1%, reported that their teachers employ the method of reading aloud to teach listening skills. Additionally, 17.1% of learners indicated that teachers utilize tape recorders as a means of teaching listening skills, while a mere 1.4% of learners reported the use of radio for this purpose. Furthermore, a significant proportion of learners, amounting to 24.3%, stated that their teachers do not employ any specific method to teach listening skills. A majority of students express dissatisfaction with their teachers' reliance on oral reading as a method for teaching listening skills, arguing that it is an inadequate approach. It is recommended that contemporary instructional tools be employed for the purpose of imparting this particular skill.

4. Testing process to check listening and speaking skills

According to the figure 4, 32.9% of students say that their teachers administer tests to evaluate their speaking and listening abilities; 47.1% of students say that their teachers do not administer any tests to evaluate these abilities; 18.6% of students say that their teachers only occasionally administer tests to evaluate these abilities; and 1.4% of students say that their teachers do not administer any tests to evaluate these abilities. The fact that just 32.9% of teachers take these skills tests is alarming, but it is insufficient for improving these skills. Teachers should set up

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assessments for students to assess their speaking and listening abilities so that they can improve.

5. Equipment for teaching listening skill

Figure 5 demonstrates that computers are used by 50.0% of teachers to teach listening skills, a CD player is used by 5.6% of teachers to teach listening skills, tape recorders are used by 11.1% of teachers to teach listening skills, and there is no equipment used by 33.3% of teachers to teach listening skills. Despite the fact that 50% of instructors use computers to teach listening skills, there is not a multimedia projector or an adequate sound system.

6. The ways of testing listening skill

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Figure 6 demonstrates that 16.7% of instructors evaluate students' listening skills using multiple choice, 33.3% of teachers test students' listening skills using short answers, 16.7% of teachers test students' listening skills using gap filling, and 33.3% of teachers assess students' listening skills using no testing system at all.

7. The scope of getting training

Figure 7 indicates that 61.1% of teachers believe they have adequate opportunity to pursue education, 27.8% believe they have very little opportunity, 5.6% believe they have no opportunity, and 5.6% believe that there should be more opportunity to pursue education.

4.12.2. Survey Questions (for Learners)

1. Information about the students of secondary level

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The data presented in figure 1 indicates that a total of 11.4% of students consistently communicate in English with their teachers. Additionally, 37.1% of students occasionally engage in English conversations with their teachers. Conversely, a significant proportion of students, specifically 45.7%, rarely utilize English when communicating with their teachers. Lastly, a small percentage of students, namely 5.7%, never engage in English conversations with their teachers. It is highly unsatisfactory that only a small number of students are proficient in English, despite the expectation that a majority of students would possess English language skills.

2. Frequency of teachers’ speaking English in the class

According to the data presented in the figure 2, it is evident that a significant proportion of students, specifically 18.6%, reported that their teachers consistently utilize the English language during classroom instruction. Additionally, 40.0% of students indicated that their teachers occasionally employ English in the classroom, while 32.9% of students reported that their teachers rarely utilize English during instructional sessions. A smaller percentage, specifically 8.6% of students, stated that their teachers never speak in English during class. It is advisable for individuals to consistently communicate in the English language, while occasionally expressing their thoughts and opinions in alternative languages. It is advisable for individuals to allocate additional time to engage in English conversation. The data is visually represented using a column chart.

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3. Ability of understanding teacher’s speech while speaking in English

According to the data presented in the figure 3, it can be observed that 38.6% of learners possess a comprehensive understanding of their teacher's speech when speaking in English. Conversely, 14.3% of learners have a limited understanding of their teacher's speech in this context. Additionally, 41.4% of learners demonstrate a partial understanding of their teacher's speech while speaking in English, while 5.7% of learners do not possess a complete understanding of their teacher's speech in this language. The data is visually represented using a column chart. A mere 41.4% of students possess a partial comprehension of their teachers' English speech, despite the expectation that a majority of students would have a complete understanding. Consequently, it is imperative for teachers to prioritize the development of these linguistic abilities.

4. Teachers’ encouragement for speaking skill

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According to the data presented in the figure 4, it is evident that 50% of the students surveyed reported that their teachers consistently encourage them to communicate in English. Additionally, 15.7% of the students indicated that their teachers occasionally provide encouragement in this regard, while 32.9% stated that their teachers rarely offer such encouragement. A small proportion of students, specifically 1.4%, reported that their teachers never encourage them to speak English.

5. Suggestions to improve speaking skill

According to the data presented in figure 5, it can be observed that a majority of students, specifically 51.4%, express a preference for engaging in English conversations with their classmates. Additionally, a significant proportion of students, approximately 28.6%, indicate a preference for enhancing their English skills through reading English newspapers and books. A smaller percentage of students, specifically 8.6%, suggest improving their English proficiency by actively listening to English news. Lastly, 11.4% of students express a preference for alternative methods such as participating in debates or engaging in open conversations to enhance their English language abilities. It is recommended that educators afford students the opportunity to engage in English conversation with their peers as a means of enhancing their oral proficiency.

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6. Problems in speaking English

It is clear from the statistics in figure 6, it is evident that a significant proportion of students encounter challenges in various aspects of English speaking. Specifically, 41.4% of students struggle with vocabulary limitations, while 40.0% face difficulties with grammar patterns. Pronunciation poses a challenge for 11.4% of students, and 7.1% find body language to be problematic when speaking English. This data suggests that all of the students have become accustomed to these issues. These are the primary challenges associated with spoken English.

5. Findings of the study

The major findings are presented below through the analysis and interpretation of the collected data:

- The majority of schools employ a combination of Bangla and English as the primary language of instruction. However, teachers employ solely the Bangla language.
- The existing textbook for English language instruction is not entirely flawless and therefore requires some degree of improvement.
- One of the most significant challenges associated with listening and speaking skills pertains to the deficiency in vocabulary proficiency. A considerable number of students

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face the constraint of limited vocabulary, which hinders their ability to articulate themselves effectively in English. Consequently, they encounter difficulties in expressing themselves accurately and experience confusion when attempting to employ appropriate words.

- The findings also indicate that students face challenges in comprehending and expressing ideas effectively through listening and speaking, primarily attributed to deficiencies in fundamental grammatical patterns and pronunciation skills.
- In the classroom, the focus is primarily on the development and refinement of two fundamental skills, namely reading and writing. Due to the exclusion of listening and speaking skills from the examination criteria, students and teachers tend to neglect these particular skills.
- One of the key issues is a lack of teaching resources. The right tools are not available to teach and test the listening skills.

6. Recommendations

This section of the study provides insights into potential recommendations that may offer an effective approach to addressing the challenges faced by Bangladeshi students in relation to English listening and speaking.

- Education professionals should not only include English spoken lessons in textbooks, but they should also emphasize the importance of practical application in the classroom.
- One potential solution to emphasize the importance of English language practice in the classroom is to allocate a portion of the examination marks to a speaking test. According to interviews conducted with certain teachers, it is argued that there should be a minimum allocation of 20 marks for the assessment of speaking and listening skills in both academic and public examinations.
- During classroom instruction, it is recommended that teachers utilize English as the primary

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medium of instruction and engage students in a variety of language tasks and activities, either in groups or pairs. This approach aims to facilitate English language acquisition through consistent practice of skills.

- English teachers should receive comprehensive training in order to effectively teach the English language.
- Teachers should provide learners sufficient of chances to practice speaking and listening in the classroom environment.
- It is recommended that teachers predominantly utilize the English language both inside and outside of the classroom.
- English is not the first language of people of Bangladesh, it is essential to foster motivation in order to successfully teach the language. Therefore, it is the responsibility of all educators to actively promote a setting that supports and encourages students in learning the English language.
- In order to effectively accomplish any task, it is imperative for individuals to possess a clear understanding of the underlying objectives. It is imperative for educators to effectively communicate the purpose of developing listening skills to their students during the process of listening.
- The inclusion of listening and speaking skills in examinations is recommended, and it is imperative for the government to take appropriate measures to assess students' listening skills.
- The existing curriculum needs to be changed to provide more courses, resources and lessons to enhance the speaking and listening practice opportunities.

7. Scope and limitations

This study focuses on the impediments to effective listening and speaking skills at the secondary level in the Dhaka metropolitan area, but due to time constraints, data are collected from only six institutions. The only skills considered are listening and speaking, leaving writing and reading out of the equation. The purpose of this research is to identify the areas where teachers and students

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struggle with listening and speaking skills. Although a great deal of research has been conducted on language acquisition, very little has been done in this area.

8. Conclusion

The study has endeavored to identify the challenges encountered by teachers and students in the development of listening and speaking skills. Based on the aforementioned findings and discussions, it can be argued that there is a certain degree of negligence towards the development of listening and speaking skills in the secondary education system of Bangladesh. Classroom practice is considered to be an effective method for teaching listening and speaking skills. Engaging in regular listening and speaking activities within the classroom setting can effectively enhance students' self-assurance, consequently aiding them in overcoming various obstacles they may encounter. The primary objective of students in language learning remains focused on attaining a favorable score rather than acquiring proficiency in the language. The main barriers for the development of listening and speaking skills include inadequate access to appropriate materials, the absence of a language lab, a lack of awareness among guardians regarding the importance of these skills, and a general indifference towards teaching these skills. Due to the absence of assessment measures for these two skills, educators tend to place less emphasis on their cultivation. Furthermore, the lack of interest among students in engaging in speaking and listening activities can be attributed to the absence of an encouraging environment. The inclusion of listening and speaking activities within the national curriculum and textbook is recommended, with the suggestion of incorporating mandatory assessments for these skills.

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